

Usability Evaluation

* Required

1. Is arrangement and size of buttons/icons/content on the screen appropriate? *

Mark only one oval.

- Very bad design, cluttered, some options impossible to select/locate/see/read device display not optimised
- Bad design, random, unclear, some options difficult to select/locate/see/read
- Satisfactory, few problems with selecting/locating/seeing/reading items or with minor screen-size problems
- Mostly clear, able to select/locate/see/read items
- Professional, simple, clear, orderly, logically organised, device display optimised. Every design component has a purpose

2. How high is the quality/resolution of graphics used for buttons/icons/content? *

Mark only one oval.

- Graphics appear amateur, very poor visual design - disproportionate, completely stylistically inconsistent
- Low quality/low resolution graphics; low quality visual design – disproportionate, stylistically inconsistent
- Moderate quality graphics and visual design (generally consistent in style)
- High quality/resolution graphics and visual design – mostly proportionate, stylistically consistent
- Very high quality/resolution graphics and visual design - proportionate, stylistically consistent throughout

3. How good does the app look? *

Mark only one oval.

- No visual appeal, unpleasant to look at, poorly designed, clashing/mismatched colours
- Little visual appeal – poorly designed, bad use of colour, visually boring
- Some visual appeal – average, neither pleasant, nor unpleasant
- High level of visual appeal – seamless graphics – consistent and professionally designed
- As above + very attractive, memorable, stands out; use of colour enhances app features/menus

Functionality

4. **Performance: How accurately/fast do the app features (functions) and components (buttons/menus) work? ***

Mark only one oval.

- App is broken; no/insufficient/inaccurate response (e.g. crashes/bugs/broken features, etc.)
- Some functions work, but lagging or contains major technical problems
- App works overall. Some technical problems need fixing/Slow at times
- Mostly functional with minor/negligible problems
- Perfect/timely response; no technical bugs found/contains a 'loading time left' indicator

5. **Ease of use: How easy is it to learn how to use the app; how clear are the menu labels/icons and instructions? ***

Mark only one oval.

- No/limited instructions; menu labels/icons are confusing; complicated
- Useable after a lot of time/effort
- Useable after some time/effort
- Easy to learn how to use the app (or has clear instructions)
- Able to use app immediately; intuitive; simple

Instructions

6. **Quality of information: Are instructions content correct, well written, and relevant to the goal/topic of the app? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Irrelevant/inappropriate/incoherent/incorrect
- Poor. Barely relevant/appropriate/coherent/may be incorrect
- Moderately relevant/appropriate/coherent/and appears correct
- Relevant/appropriate/coherent/correct
- Highly relevant, appropriate, coherent, and correct

7. **Quantity of information: Is the extent coverage within the scope of the app and comprehensive but concise? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Minimal or overwhelming
- Insufficient or possibly overwhelming
- OK but not comprehensive or concise
- Offers a broad range of information, has some gaps or unnecessary detail; or has no links to more information and resources
- Comprehensive and concise; contains links to more information and resources

